

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalar va interaktiv metodlarning didaktik ahamiyati keng qamrovda tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar hamda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'quv jarayoniga ta'sirini chuqur o'rganishga qaratilgan bo'lib, unda o'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasi, motivatsiyasi, mustaqil o'rganish ko'nikmalari va raqamli savodxonligining shakllanish jarayoni izchil yoritilgan. Maqolada an'anaviy metodlar bilan zamonaviy interaktiv yondashuvlar o'rtasidagi farqlar tahlil qilinadi hamda ular o'rtasidagi uyg'unlikning ta'lim samaradorligiga ta'siri asoslab beriladi.

Shuningdek, maqolada Suggestopedia va kommunikativ yondashuv kabi metodlarning raqamli platformalar bilan integratsiyasi, jumladan, o'yinlashtirilgan ta'lim vositalari orqali o'quvchilarning darsga jalb etilishi va faol ishtiroki qanday oshirilishi ilmiy asosda tushuntiriladi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, raqamli texnologiyalarni interaktiv metodlar bilan uyg'unlashtirish xorijiy til o'rganish jarayonini yanada samarali, qiziqarli va moslashuvchan qiladi. Shu bilan birga, maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida yuzaga kelayotgan muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari ham tahlil qilinadi.

Аннотация: В данной статье подробно анализируется дидактический потенциал цифровых образовательных платформ и интерактивных методов в обучении иностранным языкам. Исследование направлено на глубокое изучение влияния современных педагогических подходов и цифровых технологий на учебный процесс, в котором последовательно освещается формирование коммуникативной компетенции, мотивации, навыков самостоятельного обучения и цифровой грамотности учащихся. В статье анализируются различия между традиционными методами и современными интерактивными подходами, а также обосновывается влияние их сочетания на эффективность обучения.

Кроме того, в статье научно объясняется интеграция таких методов, как суггестопедия и коммуникативный подход, с цифровыми платформами, в частности, как игровые образовательные средства способствуют вовлечению учащихся в урок и их активному участию. Результаты исследования показывают, что сочетание цифровых технологий с интерактивными методами делает процесс изучения иностранного языка более эффективным, интересным и адаптивным. Вместе с тем, в статье анализируются проблемы, возникающие в современной системе образования, и пути их решения.

Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the didactic potential of digital learning platforms and interactive methods in the process of teaching foreign languages. The research focuses on an in-depth study of modern pedagogical approaches, methods, techniques and the impact of digital technologies on the learning process, thoroughly covering the development of students' communicative competence, motivation, independent learning skills, media literacy and digital literacy. The article analyzes the differences between traditional methods and modern interactive approaches and substantiates the effect of their integration on the effectiveness of education.

Additionally, the article scientifically explains the integration of methods such as Suggestopedia and the communicative approach with digital platforms, including how gamified learning tools can enhance student engagement and active participation in lessons. The research results show that combining digital technologies with interactive methods makes the foreign language learning process more effective, engaging, and adaptable. At the same time, the article also analyzes the problems arising in the modern education system and ways to address them.

Kalit soʻzlar: Raqamli taʼlim platformalari, xorijiy til oʻqitish, interaktiv metodlar, didaktik salohiyat, kommunikativ kompetensiya, Suggestopedia, kommunikativ yondashuv, Kahoot, oʻyinlashtirish, multimedia texnologiyalar, individual yondashuv, mustaqil oʻrganish, pedagogik innovatsiyalar.

Ключевые слова: Цифровые образовательные платформы, обучение иностранным языкам, интерактивные методы, дидактический потенциал, коммуникативная компетенция, Суггестопедия, коммуникативный подход, Kahoot, геймификация, мультимедийные технологии, индивидуальный подход, самостоятельное обучение, педагогические инновации.

Keywords: Digital education platforms, foreign language teaching, interactive methods, didactic potential, communicative competence, Suggestopedia, communicative approach, Kahoot, gamification, multimedia technologies, individual approach, independent learning, pedagogical innovations.

In the globalization world, knowing foreign languages has not only become just a skill, but also essential for personal and professional development. The expansion of economic, cultural, and educational relations worldwide dramatically increases the demand for foreign languages. At the same time, the rapid development of digital tools is fundamentally transforming the education system, leading to the formation of new pedagogical approaches in learning and teaching process.

In the traditional education system, the teacher was played crucial role, whereas in modern approaches, the student is placed at the center of the learning process. The student is now viewed not as a passive listener but simultaneously as an active participant, an independent seeker, unique identity and a creator of knowledge and science. This requires interactivity, flexibility, and individualization in the educational process.

Digital learning platforms are one of the main factors of these transformation. They allow students to use a wide range of information resources, work with authentic materials which related to the real life, and approach a real language environment. Through authentic materials like video, audio, and interactive tasks, students comprehensively acquire the language and also knowledge. This process is carried out based on multimodality, increasing students' levels of knowledge absorption and retention.

Another important feature of digital platforms is ensuring an individual approach. Since each student's learning speed, performance and ability vary, flexible systems can provide them with individual assignments and tasks. This makes the educational process productive and goal-oriented.

Interactive methods play a crucial role in foreign language teaching and learning process. For example, discussions, role-plays, group and pair works in teaching process students have the opportunity to use the language in real-life situations. This develops their communicative competence and fundamentally knowledge. In particular, the communicative approach focuses on learning the language not only theoretically but also practically, facilitating students' free communication abilities.

The Suggestopedia method is based on organizing education by taking into account the psychological state of students. Creating a comfortable, stress-free environment increases students' assimilation levels and performance. Using digital platforms, such an environment can be created through music, visual materials, and interactive tools, which enhances students' interest in learning. In addition to this, gallery wall is the good example of this method.

Gamification also holds an important place in modern education. Through the Kahoot! platform, lessons can be organized in an engaging and interactive way for make the lesson much more productive. Game elements stimulate competition and interest among students, increasing their motivation and also provide feedback. At the same time, quick assessment and feedback systems help reinforce students' knowledge and ability think critically.

In the digital learning process, students' activity and independent work skills develop significantly. They learn to manage their knowledge independently, search for information, distribute and analyze it. This forms the skills necessary for successful activity in the modern globalization world.

However, there are some problems in applying digital technologies into the lesson. Insufficient technical infrastructure, internet quality, and lack of digital competence among teachers can negatively affect the educational process. Therefore, it is important to create the essential conditions for the effective organization of digital education system.

The role of the teacher in the modern education system is also changing. Now, the teacher acts not only as a knowledge provider but also as a guide, motivator, and facilitator. This process requires modern pedagogical and digital competencies from the teacher.

In summary, digital education platforms and interactive methods are emerging as effective tools with extensive didactic capabilities in teaching foreign languages process. Their integration plays crucial role the educational process beyond traditional boundaries, making it much more interactive, flexible, and learner-centered. This approach increases students' engagement and facilitates deeper knowledge acquisition during learning and teaching process. As a result, students achieve a level where they can use the language effectively not theoretically but practically.

The learning environment based on digital technologies significantly boosts students' motivation and performance. These fosters a positive attitude towards learning and actively involves students in Through multimedia tools, interactive tasks, and gamified elements, lessons become much more interesting, productive and engaging, and the teacher creates friendly atmosphere for all students. the knowledge acquisition process. At the same time, students not only develop skills to independently but simultaneously manage their knowledge, work on themselves, and strive for continuous improvement for their future life.

Moreover, the integration of methods such as Suggestopedia and the communicative approach with digital platforms positively affects students' psychological state. The creation of a comfortable and stress-free learning environment improves students' self-confidence, motivation, participation and helps them learn to communicate freely without fear of making mistakes. Especially through the communicative approach, students had the opportunity to use the language in real-life situations, which is crucial for developing their speaking skills like role-plays, debates and interviews.

The introduction of gamification elements brings an innovative spirit to the educational process and their developing time. Using tools like Kahoot! to organize lessons in a game format further increases students' interest, performance, self-confidence and encourages active participation. Through this approach, students acquire knowledge voluntarily and based on interest, character, level which significantly enhances learning effectiveness.

However, some challenges must be considered when implementing digital education. Partly developed technical infrastructure, low internet speed, and under improved digital performances of teachers can negatively impact the teaching process. Therefore, alongside the introduction of modern digital technologies in the education system, it is essential to improve teachers' qualifications, performance and create the necessary conditions for teaching process.

To sum up, innovative technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, AI tutors and augmented reality are expected to take foreign language teaching to a new stage. These technologies will enhance students to learn the language in conditions as close to real life situations. Overall, the integration of digital platforms and interactive methods is becoming an important part of modern educational system, and the potential to achieve high results in science through them is continuously developing.

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